

Development and Local Validation of a Web-Based Electronic Logbook for Medical Residency Evaluation

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Abstract— The integration of digital technologies in healthcare education has enabled tools such as electronic logbooks to support the documentation, evaluation, and monitoring of residency training. This study presents the development and validation of an electronic logbook system for residents at a Brazilian Public Hospital, aiming to overcome the limitations of paper-based records. Inspired by Federação Brasileira das Associações de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia (Febrasgo) model, the system includes five core modules: user management, procedure logging, a three-stage evaluation workflow (pending, validated, rejected), email notifications, and report generation. It was developed using Flask (Python) and SQLite, following a Model-View-Controller (MVC) architecture, and tested locally for functionality, performance, and security. Although not yet deployed in a clinical setting, the system shows potential to improve resident evaluation processes. A pilot implementation is planned to assess usability and gather feedback for future enhancements.

Keywords — Clinical Education, Electronic Logbook, Medical Residency, Telemedicine, Web-based System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telemedicine can be defined as the use of information and communication technologies across various healthcare domains, allowing the exchange of valid information for diagnoses and treatments, and it can also be applied to evaluation activities and the education of healthcare professionals [1]. In this context, it is feasible to use technology as an educational tool within the healthcare sector in Brazil, serving to transform and give continuity to educational practices [2].

Technological advancements in education have led to the adoption of logbooks, which allow residents to systematically document the practices and procedures encountered during their clinical training [3]. Previous studies reinforce that portfolios and logbooks are also being strategically applied for the assurance of quality and standardization in medical training [4].

Serving as more than a simple record-keeping instrument, the logbook helps residents identify areas in need of improvement and ensures that they are exposed to a diverse range of cases and procedures. It is also a motivator for learning, encouraging residents to be more proactive in seeking out experiences they have not yet encountered [5]. From the supervisor's perspective, this technology enables preceptors to monitor resident's progress in a transparent and continuous manner, facilitating the real-time constructive feedbacks, given that the tutor can track exactly what has been accomplished, and quickly identify gaps in the student's training – leading to better outcomes for the educational program [6, 7].

Considering the importance of record-keeping and continuous assessment in the training of residents and given the potential of digital technologies to optimize these processes, the objective of this study is the development and implementation of an electronic logbook system for residents in a large public hospital. The proposal aims to overcome the limitations of traditional methods by offering an automated system that facilitates the recording of procedures, evaluation by preceptors, and generation of performance reports. In the following sections, the development methodology, system architecture, and technologies employed will be presented.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. System Request and Objective

The development of an online registration system was requested by a large regional public hospital, aiming to optimize the evaluation process of medical residents during their medical residency. The traditional paper-based logbook system presented several limitations including: inefficient tracking of procedures performed by residents, delays in preceptor feedback, lack of standardized evaluation criteria, and difficulty in generating comprehensive progress reports. The proposed digital solution aims to address these challenges by implementing an automated workflow that streamlines procedure registration, facilitates communication between

residents and preceptors, and provides robust reporting capabilities for academic assessment.

B. Reference Analysis and Requirement Definition

As a starting point, the logbook system developed by *Federação Brasileira das Associações de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia*, the Brazilian Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics Associations [8], was analyzed [8]. This reference helped to define the functional requirements of the proposed solution, allowing a comprehensive understanding of the main features expected in such systems, including user registration, procedure logging, and automated generation of evaluation reports. The requirements analysis led to the identification of five core functional modules, detailed as follows:

- 1. User Management:** Supports dual authentication for residents and preceptors, with role-based access control.
- 2. Procedure Registration:** Enables logging of medical procedures including date, description, and preceptor assignment.
- 3. Evaluation Workflow:** Implements a three-stage approval process (Pending, Validated, Rejected) with a notification system.
- 4. Automated Communication:** Sends email notifications to users regarding procedure status updates.
- 5. Reporting System:** Generates comprehensive progress reports summarizing each resident's activity and evaluations.

C. System Architecture and Technologies Used

The proposed system was implemented as a web-based application, hosted locally on a computer within a test environment. For this purpose, the Flask microframework (Python) was adopted in conjunction with SQLite as the database engine, to manage the storage of essential information such as users, healthcare institutions, and recorded procedures.

The application architecture follows a modular Model-View-Controller (MVC) pattern. The Data Layer uses SQLAlchemy ORM (Object-Relational Mapper) to manage entities such as Resident, Preceptor, Procedure, Hospital, and Medical Specialty.

The Business Logic Layer is organized into modules like `models.py`, `routes.py`, `forms.py`, and `email.py`. The Configuration Layer manages deployment variables through `config.py` and `.env` files.

Technology Stack: Flask and SQLite were selected for their simplicity and ease of local deployment, ideal for environments with limited infrastructure such as internal hospital networks.

D. Database Design and Entity Relationships

The relational schema includes secure user authentication, procedure logging with status management, and institutional references. Entities are interlinked with foreign keys to ensure data integrity. Authentication uses password hashing with PBKDF2-SHA256, and procedures follow a defined workflow from submission to evaluation.

E. Authentication, Security, and Communication Features

Flask-Login is used for session control, with cross-site request forgery (CSRF) protection through Flask-WTF. Email notifications are triggered by changes in procedure status and sent asynchronously using Python threading. All features were tested in local development environments.

F. Validation and Testing Methodology

Validation and testing were conducted exclusively in a local development environment. These included unit tests for form validation, integration tests for full registration and evaluation workflows, performance tests simulating concurrent user actions to assess responsiveness, security tests to validate protection against SQL injection, CSRF, and XSS attacks.

No tests were performed with real users or within the hospital infrastructure. All results reflect simulated usage in a controlled environment.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. System Overview and Interface Demonstration

The system has been fully implemented and validated in a simulated environment. While hospital deployment has not yet occurred, the current version demonstrates all proposed functionalities. Figure 1 illustrates the dashboard interface designed for residents. Through this panel, residents can record procedures performed during their hospital routine and monitor the status of each submission — clearly identifying which are pending, approved, or rejected by preceptors.

In addition, the panel offers a report generation feature, allowing residents to access a complete document containing all registered procedures, along with their respective descriptions and any observations made by the responsible preceptors. This functionality facilitates individual performance monitoring and provides a consolidated history of the resident's progress throughout the evaluation period.

Fig. 1. Dashboard for residents in the development environment

Figure 2 shows the dashboard for preceptors. Through this interface, each preceptor can view pending procedures submitted by residents under their responsibility. Based on the descriptions provided by residents, the preceptor can evaluate each procedure individually, approving or rejecting it according to their judgment, and recording relevant observations to complement the evaluation. In addition, the dashboard allows separate access to procedures that have already been evaluated, providing an organized view of the decision history. This dashboard also offers the functionality of generating activity reports, similar to that available to residents, allowing the preceptor to select any resident under their supervision and access a complete document with the corresponding records.

Fig. 2. Dashboard for preceptors as tested in simulation

Figures 3 and 4 show the activity report previously mentioned, which includes relevant information such as the resident's name, the originating institution, the name of the supervising preceptor, and most importantly, the list of procedures recorded and assessed by the preceptor.

Fig. 3. Example of the resident activity report feature in the development interface

Fig. 4. Example of how the report documents the resident's procedures

B. Discussion and Future Directions

The system was developed and successfully tested in a local environment, validating its potential to address common challenges in resident evaluation workflows. The modular architecture, intuitive user interface, and automated features are aligned with the hospital's original requirements. However, no practical evaluation or real-world use has been conducted to date. Deployment in a clinical environment remains a future step, which will allow for the evaluation of usability, adoption by residents and preceptors, and overall impact on academic evaluation processes.

Future work improvements include the addition of new fields for procedure registration, with the goal of enhancing the level of detail and the utility of the generated reports. A key next step will be to conduct a pilot project exclusively at the requesting hospital to evaluate the system's usability, effectiveness, and impact on practice. Following this pilot, a structured collection of user feedback will be implemented to support iterative improvements based on real user experience.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The development of an electronic logbook system for residents at a large public hospital resulted in a functional and robust prototype that addresses key challenges in clinical procedure evaluation during medical residency. The developed system meets the defined requirements by incorporating secure user management, procedure registration with status tracking, a structured evaluation workflow, automated email notifications, and comprehensive reporting capabilities.

Built on a modular Model-View-Controller architecture using Flask microframework and SQLite, the system provides intuitive dashboards for both residents and preceptors. These interfaces facilitate efficient procedure logging, evaluation

management, and performance monitoring, as well as automated report generation to support academic assessment.

Although all validation and testing were conducted exclusively in a local development environment, including unit, integration, performance, and security tests, the results demonstrate the system's ability to support the workflow and data integrity required for resident evaluation. The absence of deployment in a real hospital setting limits the assessment of usability and adoption by end users.

Thus, the system aligns with the technical and functional expectations for a digital logbook and provides a solid foundation for future real-world application and iterative improvement in clinical education processes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG), Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES), Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq) and the Grupo de Imagens Médicas for the financial and technological support provided for the development of this study and work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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